

Studies on Mixed Thiocyanato and Selenocyanato Complexes

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A new series of bimetallic mixed thiocyanate selenocyanate complexes, $M[Tl(SCN)(SeCN)]_2$ and $M[Tl(SCN)(SeCN)]_2 \cdot xL$, where $M = Co^{II}$, Ni^{II} or Cu^{II} ; $x = 2$ or 4 ; $L =$ urea (u), acetamide (actm), benzamide (bnzm), acetanilide (actn) or bromoacetanilide (Br-actn), have been prepared and characterised by the various physicochemical studies, such as elemental analysis, molar conductance, magnetic moment, infrared and electronic spectra. From these studies monomeric bridged structures for the complexes have been proposed. These structures are supported by softness calculations and Pearson's HSAB principle. Ligands prefer $M(II)$ for coordination. Thiocyanate and selenocyanate coordinate through N-end to $M(II)$ and S- or Se-end to $Tl(I)$. Stability constants of the complexes which were calculated by the shifts in carbonyl stretching frequency of amide, show direct relationship with their decomposition temperatures and reciprocal relationship with the amount of shifts ($\Delta \nu_{CO}$). Thermogravimetric analysis shows that the ligands are decomposed earlier than thiocyanate and selenocyanate.

In our earlier communication¹ we presented the study on tetrathiocyanate complexes of the type $M[Tl(SCN)_4]_2 \cdot xL$, where $M = Co^{II}$, Ni^{II} or Cu^{II} ; $x = 2$ or 4 ; $L =$ urea, amides and acetanilides. The stability of the resulting complexes have been compared with the Ag^I analogues, $M[Ag(SCN)_4]_2 \cdot xL$, on the basis of stability constants and $\Delta TE_n^\ddagger(M - M')$ values ($M' = Ag^I$ or Tl^I) and thermogravimetric analysis.

In this communication, we present the study of the coordination behaviour of mixed thiocyanate selenocyanate complexes of $M(II)$ and Tl^I , $M[Tl(SCN)(SeCN)]_2$ towards urea, amides and acetanilides in order to (i) compare the stabilities of (a) $M[Tl(SCN)_2]_2 \cdot xL$ and $M[Tl(SCN)(SeCN)]_2 \cdot xL$ (b) $Co[Tl(SCN)(SeCN)]_2 \cdot xL$, $Ni[Tl(SCN)(SeCN)]_2 \cdot xL$ and $Cu[Tl(SCN)(SeCN)]_2 \cdot xL$; (ii) study the bonding mode of thiocyanate and selenocyanate in these complexes, and confirm the preference of attachment of ligands, thiocyanate or selenocyanate, to the metal by softness calculations.

Experimental

The nitrates of Tl^I , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} , and potassium thiocyanate were of B.D.H. grade and used as such. Urea, acetamide, benzamide, acetanilide and bromoacetanilide were used after recrystallisation from ethanol. Ethanol, dimethyl formamide, dimethyl sulphoxide, ethyl acetate, methyl acetate and acetone were used after purification by known methods.

Synthesis of complexes: $Co(NCS)_2$ was prepared by the reaction of Co^{II} nitrate with potassium thio-

cyanate in dry ethanol in 1 : 2 molar ratio. Precipitated potassium nitrate was removed by filtration and the filtrate was evaporated under reduced pressure to minimum volume from which $Co(NCS)_2$ was crystallised.

$Ni(NCS)_2$ and $Cu(NCS)_2$ were similarly prepared. Potassium selenocyanate was prepared by the method described elsewhere^{2,3} and recrystallised twice from acetone. $TlSeCN$ was prepared by stirring thallos nitrate and potassium selenocyanate in 1 : 1 molar ratio in water. A white precipitate of thallos selenocyanate was obtained which was filtered, washed with water followed by alcohol and dried in vacuum.

$Co[Tl(SCN)(SeCN)]_2$: An alcoholic solution (40 ml) of $Co(NCS)_2$ (1 mmol) was mixed with a suspension of $Tl(SeCN)$ (2 mmol) in dry ethyl acetate (50 ml), and the reaction mixture stirred for ~ 36 h in moisture free condition. The green product obtained was filtered, washed with ethyl acetate followed by carbon tetrachloride and dried in vacuum. $Ni[Tl(SCN)(SeCN)]_2$ and $Cu[Tl(SCN)(SeCN)]_2$ were similarly prepared.

$Co[Tl(SCN)(SeCN)]_2 \cdot 4u$: A suspension of $Co[Tl(SCN)(SeCN)]_2$ (1 mmol) in ethanol (50 ml) and ethanolic solution (20 ml) of urea (4 mmol) was stirred for ~ 24 h. A pink complex formed was filtered, washed with ethanol followed by acetone and dried in vacuum over P_2O_5 . $Ni[Tl(SCN)(SeCN)]_2 \cdot 2L$ and $Cu[Tl(SCN)(SeCN)]_2 \cdot 2L$ were similarly prepared.

These complexes were analysed for cobalt as anthranilate, nickel as dimethylglyoximate, thallium as thallos chromate, copper as thiocyanate and

selenium as selenium metal gravimetrically. Sulphur was estimated as barium sulphate and nitrogen was estimated by Kjeldahl's method. Satisfactory analytical results were obtained for all the complexes (Table 1).

Molar conductance of the complexes were measured in dmsO using a Philips PR 9500 conductivity bridge and the results are presented in Table 1. The infrared spectra (nujol) in the range 4000–200 cm⁻¹ were recorded on a Sp 3-300 spectrophotometer. The electronic spectra (nujol) in the range 200–2500 nm were recorded on a Carl-Zeiss DMR-21 spectrophotometer by adopting the procedure of Lee³. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were made at room temperature by Gouy's method using CoHg(SCN)₄ as standard. Diamagnetic corrections were made by using Pascal's constants.

Results and Discussion

The Lewis acids and their complexes are insoluble in common organic solvents suitable for molecular weight determination and growing single crystal for X-ray analysis. However, the complexes were soluble in dimethyl formamide and dimethyl sulphoxide to some extent. All the complexes decomposed without melting.

$M[Tl(SCN)(SeCN)]_2$ ($M = Co^{II}, Ni^{II}$ or Cu^{II}): Molar conductance values (Table 1) indicate the non-conducting nature of the complexes^{1a}. Three to four bands in the ir spectra (Table 2) in ν_{CN} , ν_{CX} and δ_{NCX} ($X = S$ or Se) regions in the ranges 2120–2165, 630–740 and 410–460 cm⁻¹, respectively, indicate the presence of bridged thiocyanate and selenocyanate groups⁴⁻¹¹. It is noticeable that in the case of $Co[Tl(SCN)(SeCN)]_2$, the number of bands in ν_{CN} , ν_{CS} and δ_{NCX} regions are greater than those in the corresponding regions for $Co[Tl(SCN)]_2$ (Ref. 12). This difference in number of bands is due to the lowering of local symmetry around cobalt from T_d to C_v . In the former case, cobalt is surrounded by two nitrogens of NCS and two of NCSe, whereas in the later it is surrounded by four nitrogens of NCS. In ν_{M-NCX} region, four bands are observed due to splitting of $M-NCS$ and $M-NCSe$ degenerate bands in the range 300–245 cm⁻¹ (Refs. 14–16). Two bands were observed in the range 210–240 cm⁻¹ which are assigned to ν_{Ti-XCN} .

Green colour, μ_{eff} value (4.21 B.M.) and electronic spectral bands at about 16580 and 7850 cm⁻¹ assigned to ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ (F) (ν_s) and ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ (P) (ν_a), respectively, indicate that Co^{II} is tetrahedral in $Co[Tl(SCN)(SeCN)]_2$ (Ref. 19). A Dq value

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, MOLAR CONDUCTANCE AND MAGNETIC MOMENT DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	Decomp. temp. °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)					μ_{eff} B.M.	Mol. conductance $M/512 \Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$
			S	Se	N	Co/Ni/Cu	Tl		
$Co[Tl(SCN)(SeCN)]_2$	Green	225	7.85 (8.07)	19.72 (19.42)	6.94 (7.06)	7.30 (7.44)	51.08 (51.45)	4.21	32.10
$Co[Tl(SCN)(SeCN)]_2 \cdot 4u$	Pink	185	5.71 (6.19)	14.90 (15.29)	15.76 (16.26)	5.61 (5.71)	39.21 (39.49)	5.10	44.31
$Co[Tl(SCN)(SeCN)]_2 \cdot 2actm$	Light blue	229	7.00 (7.02)	17.01 (17.24)	8.86 (9.22)	6.32 (6.47)	44.50 (44.78)	4.26	43.40
$Co[Tl(SCN)(SeCN)]_2 \cdot 2bnzm$	Light blue	218	6.10 (6.18)	15.08 (15.26)	7.98 (8.11)	5.23 (5.70)	39.32 (39.42)	4.12	40.16
$Co[Tl(SCN)(SeCN)]_2 \cdot 2actn$	Light blue	252	5.93 (6.02)	14.72 (14.86)	7.67 (7.90)	5.30 (5.55)	37.89 (38.38)	4.6	45.86
$Co[Tl(SCN)(SeCN)]_2 \cdot 2Br - actn$	Light blue	261	5.02 (5.24)	12.83 (12.94)	6.42 (6.87)	4.50 (4.83)	33.32 (33.41)	4.44	35.80
$Ni[Tl(SCN)(SeCN)]_2$	Green	228	7.94 (8.07)	19.80 (19.92)	6.92 (7.06)	7.40 (7.44)	50.38 (51.45)	3.02	52.26
$Ni[Tl(SCN)(SeCN)]_2 \cdot 2u$	Green	230	6.86 (7.01)	16.14 (17.32)	12.16 (12.28)	6.50 (6.35)	44.38 (44.73)	3.22	50.38
$Ni[Tl(SCN)(SeCN)]_2 \cdot 2actm$	Light green	252	6.59 (7.02)	16.89 (17.34)	8.88 (9.22)	5.98 (6.47)	44.32 (44.78)	3.16	46.08
$Ni[Tl(SCN)(SeCN)]_2 \cdot 2bnzm$	Light green	227	6.02 (6.18)	15.12 (15.26)	7.78 (8.11)	5.42 (5.70)	39.31 (39.42)	3.20	45.62
$Ni[Tl(SCN)(SeCN)]_2 \cdot 2actn$	Green	257	5.90 (6.02)	14.86 (14.86)	6.78 (7.90)	5.65 (5.55)	36.41 (38.38)	3.00	46.50
$Ni[Tl(SCN)(SeCN)]_2 \cdot 2Br - actn$	Green	268	4.98 (5.24)	12.67 (12.94)	6.78 (6.87)	4.58 (4.83)	33.34 (33.41)	3.10	48.76
$Cu[Tl(SCN)(SeCN)]_2$	Yellowish green	200	8.06 (8.03)	19.70 (19.82)	6.90 (7.02)	7.69 (7.90)	50.98 (51.19)	1.02	26.30
$Cu[Tl(SCN)(SeCN)]_2 \cdot 2u$	Green	234	6.98 (6.97)	17.08 (17.28)	12.10 (12.21)	6.78 (6.87)	44.38 (44.49)	1.91	30.68
$Cu[Tl(SCN)(SeCN)]_2 \cdot 2actm$	Greenish yellow	249	6.58 (6.99)	17.21 (17.26)	9.06 (9.18)	6.98 (6.88)	44.31 (44.59)	1.90	32.86
$Cu[Tl(SCN)(SeCN)]_2 \cdot 2bnzm$	Greenish yellow	238	5.94 (6.15)	15.10 (15.20)	8.10 (8.08)	5.98 (6.06)	38.96 (39.26)	1.86	45.26
$Cu[Tl(SCN)(SeCN)]_2 \cdot 2actn$	Greenish yellow	259	5.79 (5.99)	14.56 (14.80)	7.67 (7.86)	5.69 (5.90)	38.12 (38.23)	1.80	40.20
$Cu[Tl(SCN)(SeCN)]_2 \cdot 2Br - actn$	Brown	273	5.08 (5.22)	12.78 (12.89)	6.59 (6.85)	4.92 (5.14)	33.45 (33.30)	1.90	43.76

TABLE 2—INFRARED SPECTRAL ASSIGNMENTS (cm^{-1}) OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	ν_{CN}	ν_{CO}	ν_{CX} X=S or Se	δ_{NCX}	$\nu_{\text{M-NCS}_e}$ or $\nu_{\text{M-NCS}}$	$\nu_{\text{M-L}}$	$\nu_{\text{Ag-XCN}}$
$\text{Co}[\text{Ti}(\text{SCN})(\text{SeCN})]_2$	2 160s, 2 130s	—	740s, 690m 640s, 630m	455s, 460sh 420m, 410s	315s, 320w 345s, 330w	—	250sh, 225w
$\text{Co}[\text{Ti}(\text{SCN})(\text{SeCN})]_2 \cdot 4\text{u}$	2 135s, 2 125m 2 095sh	1 637s	695m, 725s 650sh, 575sh	440s, 430s 400sh, 415m	290s, 330w	395s, 360s	235w, 240m
$\text{Co}[\text{Ti}(\text{SCN})(\text{SeCN})]_2 \cdot 2\text{actm}$	2 130s, 2 120m 2 095m	1 652s	695m, 710sh 660s, 565s	460s, 450s 410m, 420s	310s, 295m	390s, 370m	240m, 220w
$\text{Co}[\text{Ti}(\text{SCN})(\text{SeCN})]_2 \cdot 2\text{bnzm}$	2 140s, 2 115sh 2 090s	1 645s	690s, 720m 660s, 570s	450s, 440m 400s, 430m	300m, 325w	380sh, 375m	230s, 225w
$\text{Co}[\text{Ti}(\text{SCN})(\text{SeCN})]_2 \cdot 2\text{actn}$	2 125s, 2 120sh 2 095m	1 657s	700w, 730s 670m, 580w	460m, 450m 420s, 430s	305m, 325w	380s, 375sh	230m, 215s
$\text{Co}[\text{Ti}(\text{SCN})(\text{SeCN})]_2 \cdot 2\text{Br-actn}$	2 140s, 2 120m 2 090sh	1 660s	700s, 720m 660s, 565m	450m, 440s 410s, 420sh	310s, 340w	385w, 370m	245s, 215w
$\text{Ni}[\text{Ti}(\text{SCN})(\text{SeCN})]_2$	2 160s, 2 130s 2 120sh	—	740s, 690m 640sh, 635s	440s, 460s 430sh, 410s	290w, 315w 340w, 325m	—	245sh, 220w
$\text{Ni}[\text{Ti}(\text{SCN})(\text{SeCN})]_2 \cdot 2\text{u}$	2 150s, 2 130m 2 095s	1 641s	695m, 720s 640m, 590s	445s, 435m 410w, 425sh	305s, 335w	385s, 365w	250sh, 215w
$\text{Ni}[\text{Ti}(\text{SCN})(\text{SeCN})]_2 \cdot 2\text{actm}$	2 145s, 2 120s 2 095s	1 654s	690s, 710s 625m, 560m	450m, 430s 410w, 420s	300s, 320w	390sh, 370s	220s, 340w
$\text{Ni}[\text{Ti}(\text{SCN})(\text{SeCN})]_2 \cdot 2\text{bnzm}$	2 140s, 2 130m 2 095s	1 648s	700s, 705m 630s, 570sh	455s, 445s 420sh, 430s	315m, 330w	380m, 375m	240w, 210m
$\text{Ni}[\text{Ti}(\text{SCN})(\text{SeCN})]_2 \cdot 2\text{actn}$	2 140s, 2 125s 2 095sh	1 660s	700sh, 710m 650m, 605s	460sh, 440m 400w, 420sh	295m, 320w	390m, 265sh	225w, 235m
$\text{Ni}[\text{Ti}(\text{SCN})(\text{SeCN})]_2 \cdot 2\text{Br-actn}$	2 150s, 2 140m 2 090s	1 663s	695sh, 730m 645s, 530m	465s, 450s 415sh, 430s	290s, 340w	380sh, 360s	240m, 220w
$\text{Cu}[\text{Ti}(\text{SCN})(\text{SeCN})]_2$	2 165s, 2 145sh 2 120s	—	740s, 720s 645m, 640s	425s, 460s 420m, 410m	300s, 325w 340w, 315w	—	230m, 210w
$\text{Cu}[\text{Ti}(\text{SCN})(\text{SeCN})]_2 \cdot 2\text{u}$	2 140s, 2 130s 2 095sh	1 645s	695sh, 720s 620m, 565sh	455s, 420m 410s, 415m	295s, 340w	385m, 365s	230w, 245m
$\text{Cu}[\text{Ti}(\text{SCN})(\text{SeCN})]_2 \cdot 2\text{actm}$	2 135sh, 2 120s 2 090m	1 657s	705s, 715m 700m, 580s	460m, 440sh 410w, 440s	305s, 330w	395s, 370s	250s, 215w
$\text{Cu}[\text{Ti}(\text{SCN})(\text{SeCN})]_2 \cdot 2\text{bnzm}$	2 135s, 2 125s 2 090s	1 650s	620m, 710m 630s, 695s	450s, 430s 400s, 420sh	290m, 335w	380s, 375m	245sh, 220w
$\text{Cu}[\text{Ti}(\text{SCN})(\text{SeCN})]_2 \cdot 2\text{actn}$	2 145sh, 2 130s 2 085m	1 664s	700s, 715s 630s, 560s	460s, 450sh 400s, 415w	315m, 335w	380sh, 375m	240w, 220w
$\text{Cu}[\text{Ti}(\text{SCN})(\text{SeCN})]_2 \cdot 2\text{Br-actn}$	2 150sh, 2 135s 2 090m	1 666s	690m, 730w 630s, 570m	450s, 445s 400s, 420w	310w, 330w	390s, 370s	220sh, 240w

s=strong, sh=shoulder, m=medium, w=weak.

(458) calculated by Tanabe and Sugano method¹⁷ also supports this fact. Green colour, μ_{eff} value (3.02 B.M.) and electronic spectral bands at about 26 650, 15 360 and 9 100 cm^{-1} assigned to ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}$ (P) (ν_3), ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}$ (F) (ν_2) and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}$ (F) (ν_1), respectively, indicate Ni^{II} is octahedral in $\text{Ni}[\text{Ti}(\text{SCN})(\text{SeCN})]_2$. A Dq value (931) also supports this coordination¹⁸. Yellow green colour, μ_{eff} value (1.82 B.M.) and broad electronic spectral bands at about 18 760 and 14 800 cm^{-1} , indicate Cu^{II} is tetrahedral in $\text{Cu}[\text{Ti}(\text{SCN})(\text{SeCN})]_2$ (Refs. 19–21). In the case of Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes, octahedral and tetragonal geometry is achieved by axial coordination¹¹. N-end of thiocyanate or selenocyanate will coordinate to M(II) and sulphur or selenium end to Ti^I according to HSAB principle¹⁸.

On the basis of the above results we may propose the structures (Figs. 1 and 2) for these complexes.

Higher values of $\Delta TE_{\text{g}}^{\ddagger}(\text{M}-\text{Ti})$ obtained on considering ligands attached to M(II) compared to those for $\Delta TE_{\text{g}}^{\ddagger}(\text{Ti}-\text{L})$ on considering ligands attached to Ti^I , again support the structures (Table 5).

Fig. 1

M=Ni^{II} or Cu^{II}

Fig. 2

$M[Tl(SCN)(SeCN)]_2 \cdot xL$: Molar conductance values in dmsO (Table 1) indicate that all complexes are non-conducting^{1,2}.

Two ligand molecules are attached to Co^{II} Lewis acid producing blue complexes with μ_{eff} values in the range (4.12–4.42 B.M.) except urea complex in which four urea molecules are attached resulting to a pink complex with μ_{eff} value (5.10 B.M.). The later shows electronic spectral bands at about 21 740, 17 700, and 9 470 cm^{-1} due to the transitions ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_3), ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ (ν_2) and ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1), respectively, indicating Co^{II} in octahedral environment. The values of Dq, B' and β at 945, 979 cm^{-1} and 0.79, respectively, calculated by Tanabe and Sugano matrices¹⁷, also support this fact.

All the blue complexes of Co^{II} having the magnetic moment values in the range 4.21–4.60 B.M., show the presence of two electronic spectral bands in the ranges 16 000–16 600 and 7 550–8 050 cm^{-1} , corresponding to the transitions ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_3) and ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(F)$ (ν_2), respectively, indicating tetrahedral coordination geometry around Co^{II} (Ref. 19). The values of spectral parameters¹⁷, Dq, B' and β , in the ranges 440–471, 680–702 cm^{-1} and 0.69–0.73, respectively, also support this geometry.

All the complexes of Ni^{II} green in colour with μ_{eff} values in the range 3.00–3.22 B.M., show the presence of three bands in electronic spectra in the ranges 26 900–29 050, 16 400–17 350 and 10 100–10 600 cm^{-1} due to the transitions ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_3), ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ (ν_2) and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1), respectively, indicating Ni^{II} in octahedral geometry. The values of spectral parameters (Table 3) also support this geometry. Octahedral coordination geometry is achieved by axial coordination through sulphur atoms of thiocyanate ends of the adjacent molecules.

All Cu^{II} complexes are greenish yellow or brown in colour having μ_{eff} values in the range 1.80–1.91 B.M. Electronic spectra show the presence of two bands in the ranges 18 181–19 230 and 14 285–15 500 cm^{-1} which are consistent with the other tetragonal Cu^{II} complexes¹⁹⁻²¹. On the basis of

the above observations we may propose the structures to these complexes (Figs. 3a, 3b and 4) as

Fig. 3(a)

L = actm, bnzm, actn, Br-actn.

Fig. 3(b)

M = Ni^{II} or Cu^{II} , L = actm, bnzm, actn or Br-actn.

Fig. 4

Higher values of $\Delta TE_{\sigma}^{\dagger}(M-Tl)$, obtained on considering ligands attached to $M(II)$ compared to the values obtained on considering ligands attached to Tl^I , again support the above structures (Table 5).

Softness calculations: The softness values of various ligands and metals have been calculated using Klopman's equations²². The results of these calculations are presented in Table 4. A higher value of E_n^{\dagger} for Lewis acid and a lower value of E_m^{\dagger}

TABLE 3—SELECTED ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL BANDS AND SPECTRAL PARAMETERS OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	ν_3 (cm^{-1})	ν_2 (cm^{-1})	ν_1 (cm^{-1})	Dq (cm^{-1})	B'	β
$Co[Tl(SCN)(SeCN)]_2$	16 580	7 850	—	458	713	0.69
$Co[Tl(SCN)(SeCN)]_2 \cdot 4u$	21 740	17 000	9 470	945	979	0.69
$Co[Tl(SCN)(SeCN)]_2 \cdot 2actm$	16 600	8 050	—	471	701	0.72
$Co[Tl(SCN)(SeCN)]_2 \cdot 2bnzm$	16 150	7 550	—	440	702	0.73
$Co[Tl(SCN)(SeCN)]_2 \cdot 2actn$	16 260	7 840	—	459	688	0.70
$Co[Tl(SCN)(SeCN)]_2 \cdot 2Br-actn$	16 000	7 950	—	465	680	0.69
$Ni[Tl(SCN)(SeCN)]_2$	26 650	15 360	9 100	931	857	0.82
$Ni[Tl(SCN)(SeCN)]_2 \cdot 2u$	29 050	17 200	10 600	1 054	971	0.93
$Ni[Tl(SCN)(SeCN)]_2 \cdot 2actm$	28 450	17 350	10 500	1 043	990	0.90
$Ni[Tl(SCN)(SeCN)]_2 \cdot 2bnzm$	26 900	16 400	10 100	1 018	850	0.80
$Ni[Tl(SCN)(SeCN)]_2 \cdot 2actn$	28 200	16 800	10 350	1 031	986	0.90

TABLE 4—MATCHING OF LIGANDS WITH M(II) AND TI^I

Ligands	E_m^\ddagger	$\Delta E_{nm}^\ddagger(\text{Co-L})$	$\Delta E_{nm}^\ddagger(\text{Ni-L})$	$\Delta E_{nm}^\ddagger(\text{Cu-L})$	$\Delta E_{nm}^\ddagger(\text{Ti-L})$
Urea	-10.41	9.67	10.25	9.86	8.26
Acetamide	-10.57	9.83	10.41	10.02	8.42
Benzamide	-10.67	9.83	10.41	10.02	8.42
Acetanilide	-10.69	9.95	10.53	10.14	8.54
Bromo-acetanilide	-10.72	9.98	10.56	10.17	8.57
-NCS-(N-end)	-8.10	7.36	7.94	7.55	5.95
-SCN-(S-end)	-5.20	4.46	5.04	4.65	3.05
-NCSe (N-end)	-8.93	8.19	8.77	8.38	6.78
-SeCN (Se-end)	-4.41	3.67	4.25	3.86	2.26

$E_n^\ddagger(\text{Co}) = -0.74$, $E_n^\ddagger(\text{Ni}) = -0.16$, $E_n^\ddagger(\text{Cu}) = -0.55$ and $E_n^\ddagger(\text{Ti}) = -2.15$ in ethyl acetate.

TABLE 5—DEPENDENCE OF log K VALUES ON DECOMPOSITION TEMPERATURE, $\Delta\nu_{\text{CO}}$ AND SOFTNESS VALUES (MATCHING CONSTANT)

Compd.	Decomp. temp. °C	ν_{CO} cm^{-1}	log K	$\Delta\nu_{\text{CO}}$ cm^{-1}	$\Delta TE_{nm}^\ddagger(\text{M-L})$	
					(a)	(b)
Co[Tl(SCN)(SeCN)] ₂ .4u	196	1 637	4.326	50	52.89	43.06
Co[Tl(SCN)(SeCN)] ₂ .2actm	229	1 652	4.956	23	32.39	22.04
Co[Tl(SCN)(SeCN)] ₂ .2bnzm	218	1 645	4.662	37	32.39	22.04
Co[Tl(SCN)(SeCN)] ₂ .2actm	252	1 657	5.166	18	32.63	21.96
Co[Tl(SCN)(SeCN)] ₂ .2Br-actn	261	1 660	5.292	13	32.89	21.93
Ni[Tl(SCN)(SeCN)] ₂ .2u	220	1 641	4.494	46	31.49	21.21
Ni[Tl(SCN)(SeCN)] ₂ .2actm	252	1 654	5.040	21	31.81	21.46
Ni[Tl(SCN)(SeCN)] ₂ .2bnzm	227	1 648	4.788	34	31.81	21.46
Ni[Tl(SCN)(SeCN)] ₂ .2actm	257	1 660	5.292	15	32.05	21.38
Ni[Tl(SCN)(SeCN)] ₂ .2Br-actn	268	1 663	5.418	10	32.11	21.35
Cu[Tl(SCN)(SeCN)] ₂ .2u	234	1 645	4.662	42	31.88	21.60
Cu[Tl(SCN)(SeCN)] ₂ .2actm	249	1 657	5.166	18	32.20	21.85
Cu[Tl(SCN)(SeCN)] ₂ .2bnzm	238	1 650	4.872	32	32.20	21.85
Cu[Tl(SCN)(SeCN)] ₂ .2actn	259	1 664	5.460	11	32.44	21.77
Cu[Tl(SCN)(SeCN)] ₂ .2Br-actn	273	1 666	5.544	7	32.50	21.74

(a) = Total softness difference when the ligand is attached to Co^{II}, Ni^{II} or Cu^{II}.

(b) = Total softness difference when the ligand is attached to TI^I.

for Lewis base indicate greater softness. As a result, the softness of Lewis acid and base increase in reverse directions. Hence, a better match for soft-soft and hard-hard interactions will be obtained by the higher value of softness difference (ΔE_{nm}^\ddagger) of Lewis acid and base²³.

ΔE_{nm}^\ddagger values have been calculated for M-L and TI-L interactions (Table 4). Higher values are obtained for M-L interactions in comparison of TI-L interactions, supporting the attachment of ligands to M(II). Recently²⁴, the total softness values TE_n^\ddagger of M and M' in MM' (NCX)₂ have been calculated and the difference, $\Delta TE_m^\ddagger(\text{M-M}')$, evaluated. It has been shown that higher magnitude of $\Delta TE_n^\ddagger(\text{M-M}')$ is indicative of greater stability of the bridge. We have calculated the values of $\Delta TE_n^\ddagger(\text{M-TI})$, (a) for the structure in which ligands are attached to M(II) and (b) for alternate structure in which ligands are attached to TI^I (Table 4). Values for head (a) are found higher in comparison to the values obtained for head (b),

supporting the structure in which ligands are attached to M(II).

$\Delta TE_n^\ddagger(\text{M-TI})$ values for M[Tl(SCN)(SeCN)]₂.2L are found higher by 1.66 than for M[Tl(SCN)]₂.2L which show following order of stability of the bridge between M(II) and TI^I in these complexes, M[Tl(SCN)(SeCN)]₂.2L > M[Tl(SCN)]₂.2L.

Stability constant: Stability constants of the complexes for the coordination of ligands have been calculated from shifted carbonyl stretching frequency¹. These values (Table 5) are found in reciprocal relationship with the amount of shift ($\Delta\nu_{\text{CO}}$) and direct relationship with the decomposition temperatures. The following order of stability of the complexes is obtained from these values, M[Tl(SCN)(SeCN)]₂.2u < M[Tl(SCN)(SeCN)]₂.2bnzm < M[Tl(SCN)(SeCN)]₂.2actm < M[Tl(SCN)(SeCN)]₂.2actn < M[Tl(SCN)(SeCN)]₂.2Br-actn.

For a particular ligand, the stability increases from Co^{II} complex to Cu^{II} complex, Co[Tl(SCN)(SeCN)]₂.2L < Ni[Tl(SCN)(SeCN)]₂.2L < Cu [Tl

(SCN)(SeCN)]₂.2L. Stability constant of Tl^I complexes are found higher than the corresponding Ag^I analogues²⁵ showing following order of stability, M[Tl(SCN)(SeCN)]₂.2L > M[Ag(SCN)(SeCN)]₂.2L.

Thermogravimetric analysis: TGA curves of the complexes show three major inflections in the ranges 220–550, 580–850 and 930–1070° which are, respectively, equivalent to the approximate loss in the following decomposition stages,

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